

EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES

Kurbanbaeva Mirigul Jenisbaevna

Student at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, English Language and Literature, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of using games in teaching English. Games make classes interesting and exciting. They help improve the vocabulary of the language of students. Also games develop memory, agility, resourcefulness. The article substantiates the role of games in teaching English. Teaching lessons through activities requires convenient storage and easy retrieval of materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces and other props. The article provides several examples of games for use in English lessons. Using these interactive methods in English lessons more useful and meaningful. If you use active games aimed at developing students' thinking in the lessons, then you can achieve the goal set in the lesson.

INTRODUCTION

We know that teaching foreign language is difficult. I think that in teaching foreign language the role of interactive methods are very important. Because it makes the learners to motivate and keep their interests whole lessons Interactive methods include games, songs, poems, activities. Our purpose is communicated with foreigners, so first of all we must improve our communicating skills. For this, we need interactive methods, we may play different games in our lessons, it improves the learners all skills. Also games

improve the learner's vocabulary building skills. Vietnamese pupils learn vocabulary passively several factors. **First**, they consider the teacher's explanation for meaning or definition pronunciation, spelling and grammatical functions are boring. In this case language learners have nothing to do in a vocabulary learning section but to listen to their teacher. **Second**, children only think of vocabulary learning as knowing the primary meaning of new words. **Third**, pupils usually only acquire new vocabulary through new words in their textbooks or when given by teachers during classroom lessons. For example, learners find many words in a text and then ask the teacher to explain the meanings and usages **Fourth**, many learners don't want to take risks in applying what they have learnt. In summary games are useful and effective that would be applied in vocabulary classes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Teaching lessons through activities requires convenient storage and easy retrieval of materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces and other props. Ideally you should have a room large enough. If you keep your filing cabinet to the right or left of your desk, you will be able to reach at bottom three drawers without moving your chair. With small classes do well in unshaped formation or horseshoe. Very large classes might work in groupings of four, six or a double horseshoe. Try different arrangements to see what suits you and your pupils. Some suggestions for bulletin boards include: scenes of pupil's native country and customs, the four seasons, manners, health, holidays, safety, school rules and so on.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most teaching materials are not humorous. I think if there is humor in the classroom, it will be easy to explain the new theme because the learner's mood will be good. When pupils find something humorous their learning becomes more enjoyable and their motivation increases.

The lessons in the four sections of humor bring humor and English together. If we have to explain the new theme, it is no longer funny, in this case the learners are boring. The secret of the lessons is to allow your pupils to discover the humor for themselves. Our role is not to lead our pupils by the hand through the wonderful world of humor. Our role is to set up lessons where pupils can discover meaning for themselves.

Like games and humor, songs and poems are most enchanting. And culturally rich resources that can easily be used in language classrooms. Songs offer a change from routine classroom activities. Songs also give new insights into the target culture.

Like songs, poems exaggerate the rhythmic nature of the language. If a poem that exemplifies a particular structure is also a good poem, it engages the eye, the ear and tongue simultaneously while also stimulating and moving us.

Using these interactive methods in English lessons more useful and meaningful, also it is easy may to teach new words and word combinations, theme, culture and etc.

Now we will see one by one of these methods. There are many ways to teach ESL to children but one of the most exciting and rewarding ways to do it is by using English games. We learned to understand and speak our first language by hearing and using it in natural situations. This is the most effective and interesting way to learn the second language as well. The experts advise that language teachers to spend most of the classroom time on activities that faster natural acquisition rather than on formal vocabulary and structure explanations and drills. Before learning the second language we should know our first language well. Because if we know our native language well we can easily learn the second language.

Teaching English language through activities and games require a convenient storage and easily retrieval of materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces and other props. Ideally, we should have a room larger for an audio center, a quiet work center and an activity center. But if you are traveling teacher or teach in a broom closet, some where you should have a desk, closet, bookshelves and a filing cabinet at your disposal. They all help the pupils to learn the language more excellent clearer and they make pupils to motivate.

English games not only engage the children, but also through play and most of the time the pupils don't know they are learning until the time comes to show their knowledge. It truly is possible and necessary to create a classroom where the children not only learn also, they may enjoy their time there.

«There are many reasons for using games. Games are not just time filling activities. But they have a great educational value». Most language games make the learners to use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct forms. W. R. Lee says that games should be treated as central, not peripheral to the foreign language teaching program.

Games and problem solving activities, which are task-based and have a purpose beyond the production of correct speech, are the examples of the most preferable communicative activities. Such activities highlight not only the competence but only but also the performance of the learners. Both games and problem solving activities have a goal. Games are organized according to the rules and they are funny. Most games require choral responses or group works, problem solving activities, require individual response and creative solutions. Games and problem solving activities are generally used after the presentation, in the practice part, because such communication – five tasks can only be handled after mastering sufficient grammar and lexical points. Through well-planned games, learners can practice and internalize vocabulary, grammar and structure extensively.

By regarding the proficiency, age and experience of the learners, appropriate activities might be applied successfully. In sum, games and problem solving activities provide favorable usages for extended communicative practice of grammar. They are both motivating and challenging. They encourage the learners to interact and communicative. So, these activities crate a meaningful context for language use. The use of such activities both increase the cooperation and in the classroom. So far, the usage of the songs, poems, games and problem solving activities are clarified. The advantages and some key points are explained. It is now more apparent that the teaching of grammar can be supported effectively, by using such resources”. Such activities are pupil’s centered, hence by using them you give a chance to your pupils to express themselves, enjoy themselves during learning and the use the reserves of their minds.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion we can say that games are often used as short warm – up activities or when there is some time left at the end of a lesson.

If we use various motivating activities, or you teach colors which can be used to introduce vocabulary or as “Action” “Speech” at every lessons, we’ll achieve our goal.

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